

Appropriate Frequency of Error Messages

**Alf Siochi (1), Scott Hadley (2), Stan Mansfield (3), Cristina Negrut (4),
George Sherouse (5)
Frequency Subcommittee,
Error Messages Working Group,
Radiation Oncology Safety Stakeholders Initiative**

1 University of Iowa, 2 University of Michigan, 3 Varian Medical, 4 Accuray Incorporated, 5 Landauer

Foreword to the Radiation Oncology Safety Stakeholder's Initiative

The following document has been developed by the Error Messages Working Group of the Radiation Oncology Safety Stakeholder's Initiative (RO-SSI). The goal of the stakeholders group is to improve patient safety in radiation oncology. The RO-SSI meets twice a year (at the AAPM and ASTRO Annual Meetings). These meetings are attended by therapists, dosimetrists, medical physicists, biomedical and software engineers, clinical application experts, physicians, and therapy product manufacturers' experts. The attendees are affiliated with hospital-based or free standing radiation therapy departments, radiation therapy product manufacturers, regulatory agencies, independent physician and physicist practices as well as manufacturers' associations, professional associations and societies.

The purpose of the Safety Stakeholder's Initiative is to combine the expertise of all stakeholders to identify opportunities for improving patient safety in all aspects of the radiation therapy treatment process. The RO-SSI, which is independent from all other organizations, develops recommendations for consideration by the various entities with responsibilities for all or part of the radiation therapy treatment process.

In order to focus on various phases, functions and areas of the treatment process, the RO-SSI has organized several Working Groups (WGs) to concentrate on particular issues and eventually prepare recommendations. The recommendations represent the consensus of the members of the working groups. It should be noted that members of the working groups are individual expert contributors and their consent to a recommendation does not necessarily represent the endorsement of their employers.

The intent of the RO-SSI is to advise and suggest rather than prescribe actions or processes. It is hoped that the various organizations and societies with authority and responsibility in radiation oncology will consider the initiative's recommendations as they impact the respective roles of the existing

organizations. Organizations which agree with RO-SSI recommendations will be able to post their support for the document as well as implement its use in their own environments. Through this open and transparent process, all radiation oncology professionals will have the opportunity to recognize and make use of the recommendations which have been developed by this unique and independent group of vendors, clinical users and other stakeholders.

ABSTRACT

Software should be designed to display error messages only when appropriate. While systems should be designed to avoid errors in the first place, a fault management system should be in place. This can be designed with a variety of use cases error scenarios, and analytical methods such as Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA) and Fault Tree Analysis (FTA). The fault management system should have a global view of system state and analyze local subsystem states to produce comprehensive information about error states. This will allow software engineers to triage error messages and use different reporting mechanisms that are appropriate to the severity of the error (e.g. log files for diagnosis, and error messages and interlocks for errors that need immediate attention.) Error messages should be consolidated into a unified display, and other methods should be employed to prevent users from skipping past important messages. All efforts should be made to avoid message fatigue.

INTENDED AUDIENCE

Software engineers, as well as marketing and product managers of manufacturers of radiotherapy systems, are the primary personnel who would be involved in implementing the recommendations in this document. This document discusses issues of user interface design and fault management in order to provide software applications that report errors at the appropriate frequency. Manufacturers are encouraged to consider these concepts in new or revised application software and control systems. The secondary audience is the user of the application, with medical physicists having the primary responsibility of understanding these systems. Since this is the means by which software applications can report conditions that need attention, therapists, dosimetrists, and other users of the system need to be familiar with these conditions so that they not only respond to them properly but also know when it is important to work with medical physicists and service engineers to resolve issues. While some of the concepts in this document have not been implemented in commercially available radiotherapy systems, it is still useful knowledge that can help users become aware of the shortcomings of their current systems and devise means to overcome them through more robust clinical workflows.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The most basic way to reduce the number of error messages is to prevent errors from occurring in the

first place. This will require a robust system design. For example, one could simplify the choices presented to users so that they can't enter combinations of user input that lead to unanticipated software states. For a system that already exists, subsequent versions should be developed with engineers required to analyze the errors and warnings and see if there is a way to *prevent* the user from getting to the conditions that lead to these messages.

However, even the most robust system cannot anticipate all scenarios. To address the frequency of error message display, one must consider the underlying design of fault management. Systems that have a more global view of their state should be able to collect information from individual nodes (or subsystems) that only have a local view, and analyze these local faults to determine the appropriate responses within the context that generated them (e.g. user actions leading to the event, the clinical workflow where the actions took place, etc.). Consider the example of the space shuttle losing a wing versus the individual errors at localized subsystems – this “microscopic disembodied granular approach” should have analyzed the particular combination of errors and system state to determine the bigger picture (that of the wing being lost). By going to a more global view, fewer and more meaningful error messages can be provided (rather than just reporting every local node fault).

To facilitate fault management system design, use scenarios should be considered. Different clinical workflows may use devices in different ways, depending on the options and flexibility of these devices. The fault management may be different for each scenario. Scenarios should also consider different clinics (large versus small, dedicated physics support versus part time physics support, academic versus community) since they may respond to errors differently.

In the process of designing the fault management system, fault hierarchies are developed, with different levels based on 1) severity of the error, 2) the expertise required to deal with the error and 3) the appropriate authorization to recover from the error and proceed. Depending on the level, the display of the information should be different (e.g. passwords on alert messages may be required to proceed with the workflow, versus a log file for offline review).

Although triaging errors according to a fault hierarchy can reduce the number of messages displayed to the user, a poorly designed user interface can still lead to message fatigue, causing users to ignore important information that could lead to mistreatments. To prevent error messages and user responses from becoming routine, it is important to consider this “fatigue” in the safety engineering aspects of system design. FMEA , FTA, and other analysis methods should be applied to the design of error/warning/alert messages to consider the appropriate frequency and mode of error reporting. One possible approach is to avoid the use of popup dialog boxes that report normal conditions (e.g. “Save Complete!” , “Finished Processing.”). Other reporting methods for normal operations should be considered.

In addition to preventing message fatigue, one should design user interfaces so as to increase the probability that error messages are read. Here are some possible methods to achieve this:

1. Consolidate error messages into a unified display. Systems with multiple monitors should be designed so that the user knows where to expect error messages to appear (perhaps on a single monitor only).
2. Collect multiple messages into a single report when it can be done safely, instead of creating a sequential process of displaying multiple message boxes that tempt the user to click right through the set, potentially missing information. Presenting a unified single report rather than a sequence of individual messages is an option that should be considered.
3. Use log files for messages that do not need to be presented to the user but are still needed for troubleshooting. TRANSIENT fault messages that required the user to 'acknowledge' an interlocked transient condition that had already cleared is an example of presenting too many error messages. Minor interlocks that are automatically cleared by the control system should not require user acknowledgement. If the system is safe the user should be able to beam-on. All faults should be captured in a log file.
4. Use icons that show system state and allow the user to click on it to get more information (perhaps with a simpler dashboard interface, red yellow green lights versus a smiley face that starts to frown)

OTHER CONSIDERATIONS

While these recommendations were made based on ideal technical considerations, there are external design forces that also need to be addressed, such as complying with standards, satisfying government regulations, and avoiding product liability issues. This can sometimes create conflicting design requirements. For example, how often things appear on the screen may be a consequence of the legal issues. However, if they are ignored because of message fatigue, safety is compromised. Similarly, while existing standards for error messages should be used (e.g. general user interface standards), they may not be consistent with safer system designs. To handle these inconsistencies, we also recommend that a standards body consider taking on this task and create a standard specifically dealing with error messages and fault management.